

As on 30-03-2020, the following data collection and data entry procedures are recommended to add records of nutrition composition data into the knowledge base system.

Steps for data collection:

1. The general way is to find several research articles publishing the nutrition composition of the crops. Data is search by using the scientific name of the crop to ensure the right crop is taken.
2. The nutrition data may also be coming from the available food databases.
3. Ideally, a record in the '**Nutrition**' table will contain the values of **one** nutrition variable from **one** source. This is because the values published in the source might be coming from different analytical method which can cause variation in the values. The design of the database allows a crop to have multiple records of the same nutrition variable.
4. In the source, the lowest value of a nutrition variable will be recorded as minimum value while the highest as the maximum value. If the mean is not provided, the average of both values will be calculated.
5. If the multiple values are presented, the average of all the values will be calculated. This is usually be the case when the source presents abundant values of the nutrition variables which are coming from multiple crop variants or lines and a simplified value is required to be obtained.
6. In some cases, gap-filling can be done where the nutrition data of a crop can be recorded to other in assumption that they could be the same; however, the record strictly requires an indication that the data is estimated through gap-filling method. 'Data Flag' is the field to indicate this process.
7. The steps might vary according to the creativity of data collectors, knowledge capacity and time limitation. In general, the more time spent on the data collection, the more information would be retrieved.

Steps for data entry:

1. There are 15 fields to be entered, six of them are meant to be compulsory for every record.

1.1 Crop ID (Compulsory)

- This is referring to the crop common name.
- Choose the **RIGHT** crop name in Crop ID. Since the common name is used in Crop ID, make sure to check the scientific name of the crop in Crop Records.

1.2 Part (Compulsory)

- This is referring to the main part of the plant that is used for nutritional analysis.
- In this field, the selection of the crop parts is shown as a drop-down menu, thus the crop part **MUST** be chosen according to what is stated from literature.
- If there is no information on the part used stated on the source, choose 'Whole' as the main part.
- The nutrition value recorded **MUST** be from the same part. New records **MUST** be created if there is more than one part used in the analysis.

1.3 Variable (Compulsory)

- This field represent the nutrition variable e.g. carbohydrate, protein, fibre, vitamin A, calcium, iron etc. with their measurement unit.
- It is very important to avoid redundant options in 'Variable' field. If a new nutrition variable is required to be added, ensure there is no record of that nutrition variable in the '**Nutrient Variable**'.

1.4 Weight Basis

- This is referring to the weight basis mentioned in or deduced from the source.
- In the database, there are three types of weight basis that user can choose:
 - I. DW – dry weight
 - II. FW - fresh weight
 - III. Unspecified – if there is no information on the weight basis used

1.5 Value Mean (Compulsory)

- This is referring to the mean value of the nutrition variable. It is recommended to have the data recorded in a range; however, if there is limited data, record the value as one mean value.
- Make sure the value recorded from the literature is from the raw material and has the same unit as the variable unit of measurement in the 'Variable' field. If the unit is different, the value **MUST** be converted accordingly.
- All values **MUST** be recorded per 100g basis.

Additional: Important that the 'Proximate Composition' data sum up to 100, if carbohydrate data is missing/not available, ones could obtain the value through subtraction as below:

$$\begin{aligned} \text{Total carbohydrate} &: 100 - [\text{moisture} + \text{protein} + \text{fat} + \text{ash}] && \text{or} \\ \text{Available carbohydrate} &: 100 - [\text{moisture} + \text{protein} + \text{fat} + \text{ash} + \text{fibre}] \end{aligned}$$

1.6 Value Max

- € The maximum value of the nutrition variable
- € If the value in the literature is presented in a range, one can record the highest value as maximum e.g. Vitamin A RAE as: 10-50; maximum: 50

1.7 Value Min

- The minimum value of the nutrition variable e.g. Vitamin A RAE as: 10-50; minimum: 10

1.8 Data Flag (Compulsory)

- This is referring to the flag given to indicate the methodology used to derive the value.
- In database, this field is show as a drop-down menu with selections of:
 - I. Analytical value - Presented value of analysed result directly taken from the source.
 - II. Calculated value - Values from a source or multiple sources which are aggregated and processed to turn into one calculated value or value is calculated for unit conversion.

- III. Roundup value - Value is being roundup e.g. 2545 -> 2500.
- IV. Estimated value - Value is estimated from the source hints.
- V. Gapfilled value - Value meant for a crop is derived from the values of its closest relative or species.
- VI. Source presented value - Value presented in the source.

1.9 Analysis Method

- This field is referring to the method used to conduct the analysis e.g. carbohydrate by difference, Kjeldahl etc.

2.0 Pre-treatment

- Pre-treatment of the crop material before the analysis is done e.g. soaked, boiled etc.

2.1 Sample Number

- Referring to the number of samples used for the analysis

2.2 Material Source

- This field is to store information on the location where the crop materials are retrieved or provider who provides the material

2.3 Recommended Data

- Flag for the preferred data to be showcased

2.4 Notes

- This field is to store other additional information which is related to the nutritional aspects of the crop itself or explanation on the recorded data.

2.5 Metadata ID (compulsory)

- This field is to link the record to its metadata.
- One MUST create a Metadata record in the 'Metadata' table before entering Metadata ID.